

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ALAAK****FIRST NAME: LUAL****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is **the** concept of academic writing **per** the Turabian booklet?

Deleted: in accordance with

- It detailed a research outline, question, plan, prepare, reading, answers hypothetical questions, **and** literature, review. It various stages of drafting are crucial concepts in academic writing,

Deleted: ly

- Sound academic writing starts with a good introduction of what the essay entails. It captures other things such as problem, thesis and it structured in such ways to give answers to hypotheses. Ideas are required to logical flow supported by both side of arguments.¹**

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 17.

- A nonfiction Academic writing comprises of valid arguments, concepts and theories, conclusion and list of Bibliographies.

2. **What are components of research proposal to students?**

- Research is vital to all the students regardless of areas of specialization and discipline. Literature review, methodology, top approval of supervisory committee and information and facts finding and analysis.
- Research question, Literature review, methodology, problem statement, theories and concepts incorporation into a research paper.²**
- Gathering of credible sources, data collection, facts integration into a dissertation for academic requirements
- Helps in filtering sources citation, while acknowledge work of others and for readers to judge the reliability and check the accuracy of the arguments.

3. **How do Bibliography and citations become a source of disappointment to many students?**

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 220.

- Source citation and correct compilation of bibliography are important and non-compliance lead to poor grades. Lack of knowledge on correct form of bibliography and incorrect referencing causes undesired outcomes.
- Academic paper must be supported with references and bibliographies using formats provided by instructions, basic patterns, order of elements, arrangement of entries, referencing notes in text.³**
- It other functions include finding relevant data in forms of Endnote and Note-Bibliography.
- Notes-bibliography is widely used in humanities and some social sciences, while the author-date style are applicable in natural and physical sciences. It has been noted to Euclid University prefers the use of Turabian style guide, while other universities use APA and Oxford referencing styles.

4. How does the proper use of writing style play an important role in school success?

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 139-140

- The writing style includes clear layout in forms of headings and subheadings. This enhances readability and assist in coherent flow,
- It can guarantee success when supported by literature review and conforms that are preferred and considered acceptable in academic writing.⁴**
- It commences with introduction of the topic follow with evidence based arguments. The thesis or dissertation should in the introduction while arguments are incorporated in the body with a summarized conclusion of all the points.

5. **What are the roles of punctuation, and other marks in an essay?**

- The punctuation and quotation marks break the lines and assist and give respect to fundamental English rule,
- Each such as full stop, quotation marks, quotes, exclamation marks and apostrophe.⁵**
- These are important elements in separating exact words quoted in double quotation marks when quoting a passage of less than five lines.

⁴ Ibid.,373.

⁵ Ibid., 371.

6. **What makes the European Union’s writing style different from other writing styles?**

- The style guide and references of the European Union style were adopted for use in the European Union. It has its unique style of writing and formats for the benefit of EU Member States and authorizes only use of British English,
- It respects language usage such as American and British English for example consistency rather using the two interchangeably.⁶**
- It recognizes use of full stop, Commas, dashes, brackets, question mark, forward slash, apostrophe, Ellipsis, punctuation, names of people and natural phenomena in EU guide style with Turabian. Use a semicolon rather than a comma to combine two sentences into one without a linking conjunction.

7. **Is the Turabian style guide more important than Oxford or APA, and does it play a similar function in an academic fraternity?**

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 24.

- The Turabian referencing style is the only acceptable guide at Euclid University. This does not translate that other referencing style provide in Oxford and APA are not important,
- Euclid expects students to use the Turabian rule of style though health students use the Turabian or WHO rules of style or both.**⁷
- Referencing style is typical in most essays because it is used to acknowledge words or statements of authors.

8. **What are crucial concepts in dissertation?**

- The dissertation, author name, department, title, abstracts or introduction, university and place, table of contents, acknowledgements, body and conclusion/recommendations. Other such as structures, chapters, subtitles, and more development of detailed and systematic methods of investigation on a research topic are crucial,
- Organization of dissertation documents, abstract, introduction, heading and subheadings, theories and concepts integration and final conclusions.**⁸

⁷Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021, 2.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 202.

- author name, academic institution, dissertation title, supervisory committee and main supervisor, list of references and literature review

9. **What are the components of a dissertation that meet academic standards?**

- It should have precise title to acts as a guide. It should contain table of contents, outlines, chapters, research variables, participants, and setting or the research's treatment, variables, participants, and setting,
- Title is followed by chapter one with research questions, answers more other chapters may introduce new discovers and analysis of bibliographic databases. Theses and dissertations are cited much like books except for the title, which is in roman type and enclosed in quotation marks. After the author, date, and title, list the kind of paper and the academic institution.⁹**
- Consistency and coherence of the dissertation guide the researcher from losing track of the research topic.

10. **What are crucial components of quantitative and qualitative dissertation research?**

⁹ Ibid.,275-280.

- Quantitative studies rely on numerical or measurable data. In contrast, qualitative studies rely on personal accounts or documents that illustrate in detail.
- Ethics, plan and development of questionnaires are crucial elements of quantitative and qualitative methodologies, is a brief research proposal that describes what might be studied in the proposed dissertation.**¹⁰
- Both quantitative and qualitative are the cornerstones of research methodology used interchangeably during research, data collection, and data analysis. It use sample collections, analysis and tabulation, confidentiality and honest interpretation of results. Guidance on concept paper, pre-prospectus, and introduction to the chapter plan.

¹⁰ Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Tallahassee: (Florida State University, 2017), 7.

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